

CREATING LEVERAGE TO ENHANCE BIODIVERSITY OUTCOMES
OF GLOBAL BIOMASS TRADE

Quantified ex-post impacts of trade in terrestrial biomass on biodiversity

Deliverable 3.3

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

International trade in agricultural products is frequently linked to forest loss in highly biodiverse regions. Beyond local factors, the emergence of global commodity supply chains has highlighted the significant influence of demand-side factors from distant consumption areas. While international trade can indeed have adverse effects on biodiversity, it is not always detrimental. Trade can yield positive outcomes through increased efficiency in agricultural production systems, shifts in comparative advantage, or technological innovations, which may offset or neutralize negative impacts. However, the relationship is highly complex, particularly when considering the multidimensional nature of biodiversity. For instance, shifting production to more efficient regions may reduce overall biodiversity loss but could severely impact endemism if such reallocation occurs in habitats hosting endemic species.

Translating forest loss into biodiversity loss is a non-trivial task, as biodiversity dimensions often exhibit non-linear relationships and are influenced by distinct mechanisms. To address this, we build upon previous work in biodiversity modelling from WP2 to assess the effects of policies and trade dynamics on various biodiversity dimensions. Rather than solely examining deforestation as an outcome, we analyse the interplay between trade, deforestation and species richness, endemism, and phylogenetic diversity.

The net impact of trade on biodiversity - whether positive or negative - depends heavily on policy regimes and macro-economic determinants that shape demand-supply linkages. These mechanisms include demand-side preferences for deforestation-free products, supply chain initiatives promoting sustainable intensification practices, local environmental enforcement, among other factors. This complexity underscores the urgent need for holistic approaches to better understand the trade-driven impacts on biodiversity. In this deliverable, we address the following research question: under which conditions, and across which dimensions, can trade have positive or negative impacts on biodiversity?

We address this research question by adopting three impact assessments. First, we use an attributional approach across tropical regions to examine the general relationship between biodiversity loss and commodity-driven deforestation. Second, we evaluate the impacts of the Amazon Soy Moratorium (ASM) on deforestation and species richness, endemism, and phylogenetic diversity in the Brazilian Amazon. Using difference-in-differences models, we analyse the conditions under which these impacts materialize. Finally, we use an instrumental variable approach to assess how heterogeneous soy trade-related environmental preferences, particularly from the EU and China, impact species richness, endemism, and deforestation in Brazil.

The conceptual framework for all the analyses was co-designed with key supply chain stakeholders, including those directly affected by the interventions studied and those involved in the related political processes. Through workshops and interviews, the authors engaged with stakeholders to discuss how market-based governance mechanisms - such as environmental preferences in international markets, incentives for agricultural intensification and expansion practices, and the influence of traders' stickiness - affect trade-driven biodiversity loss in Brazil's soy supply chain. These discussions informed the hypotheses and governance mechanisms explored in this analysis, which also builds upon CLEVER D2.1's conceptual framework.

Our findings highlight the nuanced and multidimensional impacts of trade on biodiversity. First, tropical countries with substantial soy, cattle, and palm oil production - such as Paraguay, Argentina,

Indonesia, and Brazil - show that the majority of biodiversity loss is driven by commodity expansion rather than other factors. Given that much of this commodity production is traded internationally, trade emerges as a critical driver of biodiversity loss. Second, we also find that sticky soy traders played a significant role in mediating the impact of the Amazon Soy Moratorium on deforestation, who were responsible for almost a quarter of the total avoided soy-related deforestation between 2006-2018 in the region. Our findings show that ASM positively impacted species richness and endemism while showing no effect on phylogenetic diversity. Third, further results illustrate that a positive soy trade shock from the EU is associated with an increase in species richness (though not statistically significant) and a significant reduction in both endemism and deforestation. Conversely, a soy trade shock from China is associated with a non-significant decrease in species richness but a significant increase in both endemism and deforestation. Moreover, EU demand shocks are associated with reduced forest-to-soybean conversion and increased pasture-to-soybean conversion, indicating a focus on agricultural intensification. Chinese trade shocks are linked to increased forest-to-soybean conversion and reduced pasture-to-soybean conversion, reflecting a trend toward extensification.

INTRODUCTION

Trade in many agricultural products is associated with land use and land cover change including the loss of natural forests (Pendrill et al., 2022; Pendrill, Persson, Godar, & Kastner, 2019). These changes, driven by land-use shifts for exports and the direct exploitation of resources, have been linked to approximately 25% of projected global biodiversity extinctions (Chaudhary & Brooks, 2019). A key mechanism underlying is the influence of trade on the spatial allocation of production, which subsequently alters patterns of land use change in certain regions. As a result, increased global demand and international trade exert pressure on forests and natural ecosystems in regions where agricultural production expands to respond to the demand shocks (Cabernard et al., 2024).

According to the Heckscher-Ohlin theorem, trade liberalization and rising global demand encourage countries to specialize in the production of goods that can be produced more efficiently due to resource abundance (Baylis et al., 2021). At first glance, this specialization may appear to increase the risk of biodiversity loss in regions with extensive forest cover. However, the magnitude and nature of biodiversity impacts are heavily influenced by the governance mechanisms that mediate trade-related pressures on natural ecosystems. For instance, agricultural expansion and associated forest loss can be mitigated through policies that promote sustainable agricultural intensification. When trade-induced pressures are counterbalanced by effective environmental governance, global agricultural commodity trade can still respond to demand shocks while minimizing forest losses and related biodiversity impact in exporting regions (Dias et al., 2016; Strassburg et al., 2014).

Put it differently, exporting regions can cater to rising demand by intensifying or by expanding agricultural production (Dias et al., 2016; Strassburg et al., 2014). Both strategies may have undesirable impacts on biodiversity, but the latter results in greater biodiversity loss due to deforestation. Which strategy dominates depends on factor endowments and environmental regulations in the exporting country as well as on environmental preferences in importing regions (Henders & Ostwald, 2014; Hong et al., 2022). In many commodity producing regions in the tropics, expansion is often less costly than intensification due to poor delimitation or enforcement of property rights and environmental regulations (Pendrill et al., 2022). Demand-side environmental preferences can then help to mitigate the impacts of trade via private and public due diligence initiatives (Lambin et al., 2014). For example, if buyers of an import commodity signal lower willingness to pay for commodity flows associated with deforestation, producers in exporting regions may adjust towards more forest friendly production practices. This highlights the critical importance of policy and value chain governance initiatives in moderating the trade-biodiversity relationship.

Nevertheless, avoiding forest loss will not necessarily lead to positive biodiversity outcomes. Biodiversity is a far more complex and multidimensional concept, encompassing various attributes such as species richness, population composition, and ecosystem functionality. Ecological systems respond to threats in diverse and non-linear ways, which are not limited to forest loss alone. Hence, the relationships between biodiversity drivers and their outcomes must be rigorously identified, empirically tested, and contextually understood to enable robust assessments.

Phalan et al. (2019), for example, found that while the Northwest Forest Plan (NWFP) in the United States successfully reduced the loss of older forests to logging, it paradoxically coincided with amplified declines in bird populations associated with older forests, largely due to wildfires. Similarly, Carlson et al. (2018) demonstrated that the Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO) in

Indonesia reduced deforestation by 33%, whereas Morgans et al. (2018) found that this intervention had no measurable effect on Orangutan presence or population density. These examples point out that reductions in forest loss resulting from policy interventions do not necessarily translate into direct biodiversity benefits. As Börner et al. (2020) highlight, conservation efforts targeting specific environmental or biodiversity outcomes - such as the protection of threatened species habitats - may not align directly with overall forest cover trends. For instance, interventions could safeguard relatively small, ecologically significant forest areas that deliver disproportionately high biodiversity benefits. Hence, simplistic, linear relationships between deforestation and biodiversity outcomes should not be assumed but must instead be rigorously measured and evaluated across multiple biodiversity dimensions.

Building upon innovative biodiversity modelling approaches developed in prior WP2 work, this report aims to deepen the understanding of the complex linkages between trade and biodiversity, emphasizing both the positive and negative impacts in this relationship. Specifically, we examine how international commodity trade is linked to biodiversity loss and analyse the contextual factors and types of supply chain interventions that may yield positive or negative impact. For the global analysis, this study focuses on the global tropics, recognized as a biodiversity-rich hotspot (Jablonski et al., 2006). For the regional analysis the focus is on the South America case study of Brazil. Brazil is particularly relevant due to its significant biomass-exporting value chains and recent supply chain interventions, which allow for the application of quasi-experimental methods for impact assessment.

1. Amazon Soy Moratorium as a case study

One-third of total global forest loss can be attributed to deforestation due to permanent land-use changes for commodity production (Curtis et al., 2018). Globalization has enabled access to new areas with potentially greater comparative advantages, thereby fuelling forest losses in biodiversity hotspots in the tropics through global commodity supply chains (Pendrill, Persson, Godar, Kastner, et al., 2019). However, deforestation-free commodity supply chains are no longer a myth (Lambin & Furumo, 2023) and well-designed supply chain initiatives can also play a significant role in stopping this process (Grabs et al., 2021; Lambin et al., 2018).

Achieving sustainable food systems requires innovations that surpass the traditional focus on producers and consumers, emphasizing instead the role of midstream actors in supply chains (Barrett et al., 2020). While recent research highlights the potential of traders to serve as key actors in sustainability governance by bridging the gap between sustainability commitments and the reality on the ground (Grabs & Carodenuto, 2021), empirical evidence quantifying their importance in implementing supply chain interventions and their impact on biodiversity outcomes remains limited. We address this gap by using the Amazon Soy Moratorium (ASM) as a case study and employing econometric methods to estimate the role of traders and contextual trade attributes in this intervention. A comprehensive understanding of ASM's impact pathway could provide valuable insights to enhance the effectiveness of similar due diligence regulations such as the new European Union Deforestation-Free Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2023/1115; EUDR).

The Soy Moratorium is a voluntary non-state agreement whereby major soybean traders agreed not to purchase or finance soybeans cultivated on deforested Amazon lands. This reaction was crucial due to the widespread land speculation for agricultural production and soybean cultivation, which was considered the most profitable land use in that area (Nepstad et al., 2014). Initially, the ASM

prohibited the purchase of soybeans grown on lands cleared after July 24, 2006, a date later revised to July 22, 2008, to align with the 2012 revisions of Brazil's Forest Code. Although ASM was predominantly governed by non-state actors, including NGOs and agribusiness associations, the monitoring and enforcement is overseen by the soy working group—a partnership between soy traders, non-governmental organizations and government agencies. Using property-level information and satellite data, this working group produces an annual report identifying farms with potential ASM violations, allowing soy traders to verify the compliance of potential suppliers (ASM, n.d.).

Recent studies have estimated the ASM's role in mitigating Amazon deforestation. Evaluations of ASM's impact typically fall into two categories. Some studies attribute reduced deforestation to the ASM using distance from the Amazon-Cerrado border as a criterion for treatment assignment (Gibbs et al., 2015; Heilmayr et al., 2020), whereas others analyse the regional market share of companies implementing zero-deforestation commitments (ZDCs) to determine the timing of treatment (Gollnow et al., 2022). Although both types of studies agree that the ASM has effectively reduced deforestation in the Amazon, none quantify the specific amount of avoided deforestation directly attributable to soy traders or assess the impact of such interventions on biodiversity outcomes. Building on the literature gaps identified in D2.1, we provide further insights into how stickiness, as a governance-related mechanism through which trade can impact biodiversity, should be considered in this context.

2. Research gap on international trade literature

International trade in agricultural products has complex implications for global biodiversity. On one hand, trade can threaten biodiversity when increased demand drives land use changes and deforestation in ecologically sensitive regions (Chaudhary & Brooks, 2019; Chaudhary & Kastner, 2016). On the other hand, trade can benefit biodiversity by promoting more efficient land use through the exploitation of regional comparative advantages, allowing agricultural production to concentrate in areas where it requires fewer resources and has less environmental impact (Baylis et al., 2021). Understanding these impacts is crucial for developing policies that harness trade's positive potential while mitigating its risks to biodiversity.

A key economic mechanism behind a demand-induced effect on deforestation is a penalty on the price or even a ban for exports associated with deforestation, which depends on buyers' willingness to pay for deforestation-free products (see Hallak, 2010; Hallak & Schott, 2011 for more details on how demand preferences can impact the international trade of commodities). Although commitments to environmentally friendly practices may incur costs to producers, they can also generate value for buyers in certain importing countries. If the willingness to pay for deforestation-free production, as indicator of product quality that is perceived by buyers¹, compensates for the costs of limiting agricultural expansion, producers are more likely to increase production via intensification.

As illustrated by the literature review and conceptual framework created in CLEVER D2.1, there is a lack of empirical research focusing on how different demand preferences in importing countries impact local biodiversity loss and deforestation dynamics in producing regions. Most existing studies

¹ For example, Brazil's Soy Moratorium illustrates how environmental footprints can often serve as indicators of quality within agricultural commodity supply chains (see Gibbs et al., 2015; Heilmayr et al., 2020; Soterroni et al., 2019).

focus only on deforestation but do not differentiate between demand preferences by importing countries (DeFries et al., 2010; Leblois et al., 2017). Some other studies allow for variation in preferences, but employ correlational analysis rather than causal inference (Da Silva et al., 2023; Zu Ermgassen et al., 2020) or focus on a specific importing country as a case study (Carreira et al., 2024). This constitutes a gap in our understanding of the role of demand preferences on the impact of international trade on biodiversity loss and deforestation.

OBJECTIVES

This deliverable (D3.3) presents counterfactual estimates of biodiversity impacts associated with non-food biomass trade, focusing on policy regimes and macro-economic determinants as moderating factors. More specifically, we investigate the role of demand-side preferences from different international markets and value chain governance mechanisms established by soy traders, which serve as proxies for both moderating factors. D3.3 fulfils the following objectives:

1. To employ a co-design approach to the conceptual framework (D2.1), outlining the mechanisms through which biomass trade affects biodiversity.
2. To link LULCC from agricultural commodity production to biodiversity loss across the global tropics based on an attributional approach informed by D2.2-4.
3. To estimate ex-post impacts of trade in biodiversity loss, by looking at the Amazon Soy Moratorium in Brazil - a trade-related value chain governance intervention – and its impacts on deforestation and selected biodiversity indicators (from D2.3)
4. To assess the influence of heterogeneous environmental preferences in soy-importing countries, particularly the European Union (EU) and China, on biodiversity indicators and deforestation in Brazil.

Through these analyses, D3.3 contributes to CLEVER Objective II: **“Provide empirical evidence for causal relationships between value chain governance initiatives and biodiversity impacts as well as related policy spillovers”**.

DATA AND METHODS

This section describes the co-design process of the conceptual framework in collaboration with stakeholders and provides an overview of the methods employed to quantify the causal impacts of non-food biomass trade on biodiversity. First, we outline the stakeholder engagement and co-design process that informed the development of the mechanism framework for counterfactual analysis. Second, we detail the methods applied in the empirical analyses.

1. Conceptual framework, co-design and stakeholder engagement

The creation of the mechanism framework for counterfactual analysis is primarily based on D2.1, “Literature review and conceptual framework on mechanisms of how biomass trade affects biodiversity”, milestone M5, active discussions with WP4 and WP5, and exchanges with the stakeholder reference groups to identify specific policy treatments. Specifically, the first step was to shed light on research gaps across scientific fields by reviewing recent literature linking agricultural trade and biodiversity. This review identified various thematic areas that help explain potential trade-driven impacts on biodiversity. Subsequently, a comprehensive set of hypotheses was developed to identify the conditions that determine the potential leverage of different policies and governance mechanisms. Finally, the framework underwent refinement through co-design and stakeholder engagement activities. This deliverable focuses on providing additional details about the latter steps, as the earlier material has already been made publicly available in the CLEVER [repository](#).

The co-design activities conducted within WP3 with the support of the WP8 (T8.3) were pivotal for the development of the empirical analysis presented in D3.3. We strategically engaged with stakeholder initiatives to define the hypotheses for the impact assessments and to design an empirical approach that closely reflects the realities faced by practitioners. This process employed two specific co-design and stakeholder engagement methodologies: two workshop discussions with stakeholders and one-on-one interviews.

Workshop 1: *Toward compliance with the EU Deforestation Regulation: Criteria, Tools, and Open Questions.*

Date: November 13, 2023

Hybrid event: online and in-person at the University of Bonn, Germany.

Participants: 60 stakeholders, including Brazilian and international actors representing all sectors - public authorities, private companies, certifiers, NGOs, company associations, and research organizations.

Goal of the event: The goal was to open a dialogue about the EU’s new directive aimed at eliminating products linked to deforestation from EU markets (EUDR). Participants identified challenges and opportunities for building transparent, ethical supply chains. They also discussed potential partnerships and initiatives to help companies meet the directive’s environmental standards. A brief outlining recommended actions was prepared following the workshop. This brief was shared with relevant authorities to inform ongoing consultations.

Contribution to D3.3: A dedicated breakout group focused on the soybean sector in Brazil allowed us to engage closely with stakeholders directly involved to clarify questions on new regulatory requirements, existing and required traceability measures, risk assessment, mitigating actions, and supply chain segregation. This dialogue significantly contributed to refining our hypotheses and empirical analyses in D3.3.

Workshop 2: Roundtable European Deforestation Regulation (EUDR) – Challenges and traceability solutions

Date: 28 and 29 February 2024

Hybrid event: online and in-person in Brasília, Brazil.

Participants: Brazilian and international actors representing all sectors—public authorities, private companies, certifiers, NGOs, company associations, and research organizations.

Goal of the event: The main goal of the event is to discuss recent advances and remaining gaps in the technical implementation of the EUDR with a focus on Brazilian soy and beef exports. The event aimed to identify possible risk mitigating measures that can be implemented to reduce deforestation risks to negligible levels, and better understand the minimum quality criteria (e.g. temporal & spatial accuracy) for due diligence documentation and basic principles for the development of risk mitigation measures.

Contribution to D3.3: Given the specific emphasis on the Brazilian soybean sector and the participation of relevant stakeholders, the discussions during the event assisted us in refining the hypotheses and mechanisms through which trade can be utilized to amplify the positive impacts of environment-related regulations. While the EUDR is not the focal point of our ex-post impact evaluation, insights from stakeholders' expectations and timely debates on this topic enhanced the design of our empirical approach on the ex-post impacts of trade in terrestrial biomass on biodiversity.

Finally, we conducted five additional one-on-one interviews to address remaining gaps in the empirical approach and discuss preliminary findings, with the aim of refining the analyses. The stakeholders invited for these interviews were selected based on their expertise in the soy supply chain and environmental regulatory framework in Brazil. Participants included representatives from the private sector, such as companies and associations, as well as NGOs. The interview guide used is provided in Appendix A.

2. Attributional approach

This section explains how commodity-driven deforestation is identified as a driver of biodiversity loss through an attributional approach, leveraging high spatiotemporal resolution data for the global tropics.

The biodiversity loss data used in this analysis was compiled from D2.2, D2.3, and D2.4. To quantify biodiversity loss associated with land-use changes, WP2 compared biodiversity in two scenarios: one representing current conditions and another establishing a baseline. The difference between these scenarios represents the biodiversity loss to date. The baseline model emphasizes vegetation structure as a predictor of biodiversity, enabling us to estimate biodiversity changes due to land-use modifications (see D2.2, D2.3 for additional methodological details). Our final data cover the tropics at ~1 km spatial resolution in three specific time periods: 2000–2005, 2005–2010, and 2010–2015. We mapped all pixels exhibiting biodiversity loss identified by the dimension of species richness in at least one of these periods.

To attribute biodiversity loss to commodity production, we used data from Curtis et al. (2018), who developed a decision-tree model based on high-resolution Google Earth imagery analysis. Their model classifies the primary drivers of forest disturbance globally from 2000 to 2015 at a 10 km x 10 km resolution. Categories of drivers include commodity-driven deforestation, shifting agriculture,

forestry, wildfire, and urbanization. We integrated this classification with our biodiversity loss dataset to identify areas where commodity production was the primary driver of biodiversity loss. The two spatial datasets were overlaid to assess this relationship.

3. Ex-post econometric analysis

Ex-post econometric analysis provides critical insights into the drivers of biodiversity loss by estimating the population-scale net effects of trade-related pressures. These approaches move beyond identifying proximate causes to reveal the underlying drivers of biodiversity decline. This section outlines the methods used to analyse the impacts of the Amazon Soy Moratorium and the heterogeneous effects of soy export-market preferences on biodiversity and forest loss in Brazil. We apply quasi-experimental methods, including difference-in-differences and instrumental variable regression approaches, to rigorously identify these effects.

3.1. Impacts of the Amazon Soy Moratorium on biodiversity outcomes

Our study focused on municipalities located in the Brazilian Amazon and Cerrado biomes. We restricted our analysis to municipalities whose city halls fall within 200 km of the Amazon-Cerrado biome. By limiting our focus to these locations, we exclude more distant areas of both biomes, where very different drivers of deforestation also take place. Parts of the data detailed below were already published in [D3.1](#) (“Database on biomass trade, production, demand, biodiversity proxies”). Data on biodiversity outcomes were derived from previous work of CLEVER ([D2.2](#) and [D2.3](#)).

As an innovation within CLEVER, these new biodiversity metrics facilitate the assessment of average effects of policy interventions. In this study, we assess the average impact on three biodiversity dimensions at the municipality-year level: species richness, endemism, and phylogenetic diversity. These metrics are based on the novel approach outlined in CLEVER Deliverable D2.2 and D2.3, which integrate sampling effort into biodiversity modelling. This methodology offers two significant contributions. First, it enhances the reliability of biodiversity metrics by accounting for sampling biases that may otherwise distort the construction of biodiversity dimensions. Second, this modelling strategy allows for flexible adjustment of the spatiotemporal scale of biodiversity metrics, thereby enabling straightforward impact evaluations of policy interventions, which often require aggregate measures at the level of supply chains, municipalities, regions, or countries.

Data on forest losses

Across our study area, we extracted a variety of variables from two main data sources (Ilière et al., 2022; *Project MapBiomass - Collection 8 of Brazilian Land Cover & Use Map Series.*, n.d.). We compiled information on deforestation (km²) of primary forest vegetation, soy crop and pasture area for a set of Brazilian municipalities (Figure 1) from 2004 to 2018.

Empirical approach

We focus our study on municipalities whose city halls fall within 200 km of the Amazon-Cerrado biome border (Fig. 1). Here we run a difference-in-difference (DiD) model to isolate post-ASM changes in biodiversity outcomes. While this approach is useful for testing the total effect of the policy, it does not allow us to isolate the specific impact of the ASM from the effects of concurrent biome-specific policy interventions (Assunção et al., 2020, 2023; West & Fearnside, 2021), even when controlling for additional confounding factors. We thus run a DiD with mediation analysis to accurately isolate the impact of the ASM. We use the traded soy volume of the largest five (Top 5) soy traders in 2004-2018 as a mechanism through which the ASM curbs deforestation. We argue that these traders were more likely to support the implementation of the policy because of their higher levels of stickiness and potential sunk costs. Examples of this low level of mobility include pre-2006 investments in infrastructure and transportation logistics, such as Cargill’s 20 million US dollars investment in a port in Santarém, Pará (Greenpeace, 2016). These traders include Bunge, Cargill, ADM, Louis Dreyfus Company, and Amaggi, which concentrate 54% of the market share of all internationally traded Brazilian soy exports between 2004 and 2018.

Figure 1. Study area

Note: Our study focuses on municipalities whose city halls fall within 200 km of the Amazon-Cerrado biome border. We exclude municipalities that are crossed by the border. Our analysis measures the impact of the ASM by comparing post-ASM changes in deforestation rates among municipalities in the Amazon biome relative to those in Cerrado.

By concentrating on areas near the Amazon-Cerrado biome, we aim to identify the impact of ASM while also controlling for other deforestation drivers such as proximity to roads, markets, infrastructure, and local weather and vegetation factors. We analyse deforestation trends at the municipal scale, leveraging municipality and year fixed effects to control for additional confounding factors. Furthermore, our study primarily focuses on trade attributes, which confines us to this spatial scale due to the limitation that trade data only extends back to the municipality of origin, rather than

to the specific farms where soy was produced.

Our primary model specification integrates both spatial and temporal variation to assess ASM effects on deforestation. We compare the trends of biodiversity outcomes and deforestation between two groups of municipalities - those located in the Amazon and those in the Cerrado - using annual data from before and after ASM implementation in 2006. We analyse this model running municipality-year level regressions with two-way fixed effects (TWFE), as represented by Equation 1:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Amazon_i \times PostASM_t + Z'_0 \times \delta_t + \gamma_i + \delta_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

where Y_{it} represents the outcome of interest, which measures the three biodiversity dimensions - species richness, endemism, and phylogenetic diversity - or primary forest vegetation (in km^2) per municipality i and year t . $Amazon_i$ is a binary variable indicating whether the municipality falls within the Amazon biome. $PostASM_t$ identifies the post-ASM period starting in 2006. Z'_0 is a vector of time-invariant municipality-specific conditions, including soy crop area and pasture area measured in 2004, along with a set of state dummies. γ_i and δ_t represent a set of municipality and year fixed effects, respectively. ε_{it} is our error term, clustered at the municipality level. The parameter of interest is β_1 , which isolates the post-ASM deviation in outcome variables that occurs on municipalities located in the Amazon biome. Under a set of assumptions, this coefficient can be interpreted as the average treatment effect of the ASM. We expect β_1 to be negative, reflecting a decrease in losses of biodiversity and of primary forest vegetation post-ASM.

Traders as mediators

We evaluate the extent to which the reduction in deforestation associated with the ASM can be attributed to these stickier soy traders. To measure this indirect effect, we use the difference of coefficients approach (Judd & Kenny, 1981). In line with the mediation analysis literature, this design yields the same results when employing the product of coefficients approach (MacKinnon et al., 1995; Sobel, 1982).

To assess the extent to which the reduction in deforestation can be attributed to sticky soy traders affected by the ASM, we introduce another variable measuring the influence of the five largest soy traders. This is expressed in Equation 2 as follows:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Amazon_i \times PostASM_t + \beta_2 Top5_Traders_{it} + Z'_0 \times \delta_t + \gamma_i + \delta_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

$Top5_Traders_{it}$ identifies the volume of soy exports the largest five soy traders trade per municipality i and year t . Following the difference of coefficients approach (Judd & Kenny, 1981), we measure the indirect effects of ASM due to these soy traders by taking the difference of the β_1 in Eq. 1 and β_1 in Eq. 2. The difference between these two coefficients measures the variation that is captured by the additional mediator measured with β_2 in Eq. 2. We then tested the statistical significance of these indirect effects by employing a percentile bootstrap method (Chen & Fritz, 2021).

3.2. Heterogeneous effects of soy export-market preferences on biodiversity outcomes

We collect data on trade flows of soy exports, deforestation and all the control variables at the municipality-year level for 5560 Brazilian municipalities that existed throughout the entire period from 2004 to 2018. Parts of the data detailed below were already published in D3.1. Biodiversity outcomes were derived from D2.2 and D2.3. Across our study area, we extracted information on deforestation (hectares) of primary forest vegetation from *Project MapBiomias - Collection 8 of Brazilian Land Cover & Use Map Series*. (n.d.).

Data on soy exports

To examine how demand preferences from different destination markets impact local deforestation, we utilize subnational trade flow data of soy exports from Brazilian municipalities to the EU and China. While international commodity trade flows are typically recorded at the ports of export, we use data from the innovative TRASE database. This database allows us to identify crucial information for our analysis, including annual export volumes, destination markets, export ports, and the specific municipalities where the exported soy was produced. We construct two separate treatment variables to isolate each market's demand preference: 1) the volume (in tonnes) of soy exports shipped to the EU, and 2) the volume (in tonnes) of soy exports shipped to China.

Additional variables

We collect additional control variables on the number of hectares of forest area and pasture area from *Project MapBiomias (Collection 6 of Brazilian Land Cover & Use Map Series.*, n.d.), the share of gross domestic product (GDP) from agriculture from the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE), and the number of registered exporting companies from the Ministry of Economy in Brazil. All control variables are standardized to $N(0,1)$ and used as initial conditions, i.e., time-invariant and measured in 2004.

Empirical approach

Instrument (shift-share measure)

The causal relationship between trade and biodiversity loss and deforestation is notoriously hard to disentangle. On the one hand, increases in the demand for agricultural commodities in importing regions can translate, via trade relationships, into higher demand for land in exporting regions (Pendrill et al. 2019). On the other hand, deforestation and related biodiversity loss can increase prospects for trade if it results from exporting regions' investments in roads or technological innovation aimed at making their agricultural sectors more competitive (Barber et al., 2014; Pfaff et al., 2007). Trade, deforestation and biodiversity loss are thus often simultaneously determined.

As simultaneity is present in the relationship, we use an instrumental variable and a 2SLS estimation procedure per export destinations – the EU and China in our case. While alternative methodologies could potentially allow us to consolidate all estimates into a single model, some specific idiosyncrasies of our context make this particularly challenging. For instance, we do not adopt a gravity approach because the geographical distances between most Brazilian municipalities and their destination countries do not vary significantly in many cases. We also do not use a multi-level approach, which, while allowing for variance decomposition across time, municipalities, and destination countries, would require a higher number of destination countries and would introduce complexities when combined with a shift-share IV design. Hence, we opt for on a shift-share approach to instrument trade in two separate models for each the EU and China (Bartik, 1991).

The shift-share approach, also known as the Bartik-type instrument, has recently been used in deforestation studies (see Carreira et al., 2024). This measure encapsulates a weighted combination of initial exposure (or share) and an exogenous shock to enable a path to uncover causality. By using a shift-share instrument, one can create a sufficient condition to identify causal effects, while effectively addressing the inherent endogeneity within local supply characteristics (see Borusyak et al., 2022; Goldsmith-Pinkham et al., 2020).

We construct the shift-share measure using competition shocks captured by market share of soybean exports shipped from countries other than Brazil (i.e., competition) to the EU and China (shift) and time-invariant local agro-climatic conditions for soy cultivation (share) at the municipality level. The combined shift-share measure varies across municipalities due to differences in local soy suitability and across time in response to export market dynamics. As our shift measure (derived from international competition) is constant across municipalities in a given year, variation in exposure to the shock must come from the shares (municipal level suitability for soy). Soy suitability thus effectively weighs annual export market exposure. Our lagged shift-share measure (Eq. 3), $SoyCompetitionExposure_{it-1}$, is then derived by interacting international trade competition in year $t - 1$ with suitability for soy in municipality i .

$$SoyCompetitionExposure_{it-1} = CompetitorsShare_{t-1} \times SoySuitability_i, \text{ (Eq. 3)}$$

The shift component ($CompetitorsShare_{t-1}$) captures competition shocks captured by the market-share (%) of soy imports volume of EU or China from sourcing countries other than Brazil from FAO database. We use competition shocks from the previous year ($t-1$) as we assume that the signal in deforestation resulting from expectations based on a demand shock takes some time to materialize. Our share measure ($SoySuitability_i$) is based on average suitability for soy that captures the potential yields under rainfed conditions and high input level per municipality i from the FAO-GAEZ data. The inherent characteristics of the soy sector in Brazil serve as the foundational basis for this decision. Most of soy production in Brazil is based on high input intensity, i.e., it adopts improved or high yielding varieties, mechanization where possible, and optimal applications of agrochemicals. Furthermore, as irrigation is not common in the Brazilian soy plantations, we use the soy suitability under rainfed conditions in all phases.

Our shift-share measure assigns higher values to locations more suitable for soybean cultivation. Regions with greater potential for soy production are thus more sensitive to competition shocks, whereas locations with lower suitability are less sensitive. The validity of our empirical analysis hinges on the relevance of the shift-share as an instrument and the exclusion restriction.

The relevance condition requires that the instrument effectively explains the variance of the treatment variable. In our case, this requirement translates to statistically significant coefficients when regressing soy exports on the shift-share measure. Specifically, we expect that higher competition with other soy-exporting countries will translate into lower soy exports from Brazilian municipalities. Put it differently, we expect a negative coefficient when regressing soy exports on our shift-share instrument.

The exclusion restriction, on the other hand, posits that the instrument influences the outcome variable solely through its effect on the treatment variable. Put differently, the instrument must not directly impact the outcome, nor should it be correlated with any unobserved factors that might

confound the relationship between the treatment and outcome.

Regression specification

We use a 2SLS estimation procedure to estimate the impact of soy trade on biodiversity outcomes and on deforestation. We regress biodiversity outcomes and forest cover change across Brazilian municipalities on soy exports to the EU and China. We run separate models: one for export flows to the EU and another for the export flows to China.

The first stage of our 2SLS estimate is,

$$SoyExports_{it} = \alpha_i + \gamma_t + \beta SoyCompetitionExposure_{it-1} + Z_{i0} \times t \delta + \varepsilon_{it}, \text{ (Eq. 4)}$$

where $SoyExports_{it}$ measures the volume (in thousands of tonnes) of soy exports shipped to the EU or China from municipality i in year t . $SoyCompetitionExposure_{it-1}$ is the soy competition exposure, which varies across municipalities and years. Z_{i0} captures additional differential time trends by accounting for initial conditions in 2004. Specifically, we include the initial forest area, pasture area, share of gross domestic product (GDP) from agriculture, and number of registered exporting companies. The inclusion of municipality-specific time trends reduces the risk of potential biases arising from these initial conditions, which could correlate with underlying socio-economic structures that jointly impact biodiversity loss, deforestation and exporting trends, thereby potentially compromising the validity of the shift-share measure as a valid instrument. α_i represents municipality fixed effects that control for all sources of time-invariant municipality heterogeneity and γ_t are year fixed effects. ε_{it} is the error term, clustered at the municipality level to account for serial correlation of errors within the same municipality. Finally, we expect β to be negative, reflecting a decrease in soy exports from Brazilian municipalities due to higher competition from other soy-exporting countries.

The second stage of our 2SLS estimate is,

$$Y_{it} = \alpha_i + \gamma_t + \lambda Soy\widehat{Exports}_{it} + Z_{i0} \times t \delta + v_{it}, \text{ (Eq. 5)}$$

where Y_{it} represents the outcome of interest, which measures either the two biodiversity dimensions - species richness and endemism – or primary forest vegetation (in hectares) per municipality i and year t . $Soy\widehat{Exports}_{it}$ is the estimated trade values from the first stage. The sign of λ in the case of EU model shows the impact of a positive EU trade shock on local biodiversity and deforestation in Brazil and in the case of China model shows the impact of a positive China trade shock on local biodiversity and deforestation in Brazil. We expect λ to be negative in the EU model, reflecting drops in land use pressure due to greater exposure to EU demand preferences, and positive in the China model, indicating increases in deforestation and biodiversity loss from greater exposure to Chinese demand preferences. α_i are municipality fixed effects, γ_t are year fixed effects, and Z_{i0} captures the same initial conditions as explained in Eq. 4. v_{it} is the error term, clustered at the municipality level.

RESULTS

1. Attributional approach

The expansion of agricultural commodities is often linked to deforestation in highly biodiverse regions within the tropics and subtropics, contributing to both global and regional climate change (Busch & Ferretti-Gallon, 2023; Pendrill et al., 2022). Figure 2 shows the proportion of biodiversity loss, measured through changes in species richness, that can be attributable to commodity production versus other drivers. The figure includes only countries located in the tropics where at least 20% of total biodiversity loss is linked to commodities. Notably, countries with significant shares of soy, cattle, and palm oil production exhibit a dominant role of commodity expansion in biodiversity loss. For instance, Paraguay, Argentina, Indonesia, and Brazil demonstrate that the majority of their biodiversity loss is commodity-driven.

Figure 2. Terrestrial biodiversity loss across the tropics by country

Figure 3 provides a complementary perspective, displaying all pixels where biodiversity loss occurred, whether driven by commodity production or other factors. In line with Figure 2, it is possible to observe that commodity-driven biodiversity loss is concentrated in specific areas across the tropics.

Figure 3. Terrestrial biodiversity loss across the tropics

2. Ex-post econometric analysis

2.1 Impacts of the Amazon Soy Moratorium on biodiversity outcomes

Table 1 presents the findings on deforestation as the outcome variable. We show that stickier soy traders were responsible for ~525 km² of the avoided deforestation of primary forest from the ASM between 2006-2018 when using the volume of soy exports as a mediator. This accounts for about 23% of the total avoided soy-related deforestation in the Brazilian Amazon, as indicated by existing empirical estimates that use ZDC to define exposure to the ASM (Gollnow et al., 2022). Our econometric models isolate and quantify the share of these stickier soy traders in ASM's impacts by comparing how much of the total effect from the relative trends in deforestation rates across biomes is captured by the traded volume of the top five traders in the Brazilian soy supply chain (Table 1).

Table 1. Baselines estimates of mediation analysis

VARIABLES	(1)	(2)
	Deforestation of primary forest vegetation (km ²)	Deforestation of primary forest vegetation (km ²)
ASM	-9.21** (3.84)	-8.96** (3.79)
Volume of soy exports from Top 5 soy traders		-0.0000339* (0.0000177)
Observations	4,470	4,470
Municipality FE	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES
2004 soy area x Year FE	YES	YES
2004 pasture area x Year FE	YES	YES
State dummies x Year FE	YES	YES

Notes: (a) robust standard errors in parentheses and clustered at the municipality level. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

Table 2 presents the results for species richness, endemism, and phylogenetic diversity. Beyond the observed effects on deforestation, our analysis indicates that the ASM has had a positive impact on increasing species richness and endemism, while showing no effect on phylogenetic diversity. These findings align with our previous results, illustrating that supply chain interventions aimed at reducing deforestation can also yield positive outcomes for overall biodiversity.

Table 2. ASM impact on biodiversity outcomes

VARIABLES	(1)	(2)	(3)
	Species richness	Endemism	Phylogenetic diversity
ASM	0.60* (0.32)	0.62*** (0.18)	-0.01 (0.02)

Observations	4,470	4,470	4,470
Municipality FE	YES	YES	YES
Year FE	YES	YES	YES
2004 soy area x Year FE	YES	YES	YES
2004 pasture area x Year FE	YES	YES	YES
State dummies x Year FE	YES	YES	YES

Notes: (a) robust standard errors in parentheses and clustered at the municipality level. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

2.2 Heterogeneous effects of soy export-market preferences on biodiversity outcomes

Here, we address this gap by focusing on how relationship between trade and deforestation is mediated by different environmental preferences on the demand side using the example of soybean exports from Brazil, the top global soy exporter. Specifically, we quantify the impacts of changes in demand for Brazilian soy in the EU and China on local biodiversity loss and deforestation in Brazil. As of 2019, Brazil is the largest exporter of soy supplying about 47% of globally traded soy (De Maria et al., 2022). This and the availability of export flow data at municipality level make Brazil the ideal focus country to test our hypotheses. EU and China jointly accounted for approximately 57% of the Brazilian soy volume exports in 2020 (TRASE database). These two import regions do not only have sizeable market shares in Brazilian soy, but they also place different levels of importance on sustainable production practices in their sourcing regions (Pendrill et al., 2019; Zu Ermgassen et al., 2020).

Our empirical analysis captures the dynamics of biodiversity outcomes and deforestation in a yearly panel of Brazilian municipalities between 2004 and 2018. Conditional on municipality and year fixed effects, we estimate how biodiversity and forest cover respond to changes in soy exports to the EU and China. As the relationship between biodiversity, deforestation and soy exports is likely endogenous, we employ an instrumental variable regression using a shift-share measure. To identify the effects of demand preferences, we run separate two-stage least squares (2SLS) regressions using two different country-specific shift-share measures. Our shift-share measure combines temporal variation of market share of soybean exports shipped from countries other than Brazil (i.e., competition) in these two destination markets in the previous year (shift) with time-invariant local agro-climatic conditions to grow soybeans at the municipality level (share). For the first stage, we assume that higher competition from other producing regions translates into lower soy exports from Brazilian municipalities. For the second stage, we expect diverging effects of soy trade with the EU and China on the local biodiversity and deforestation dynamics in Brazil. The impact of soybean exports to the EU and China on biodiversity and deforestation in Brazil are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Effects of soy exports on biodiversity and deforestation

VARIABLES	EU				China			
	(1) <i>Soy Exports_EU_{it}</i>	(2) <i>SpeciesRichness_{it}</i>	(3) <i>Endemism_{it}</i>	(4) <i>Deforestation_{it}</i>	(5) <i>Soy Exports_China_{it}</i>	(6) <i>SpeciesRichness_{it}</i>	(7) <i>Endemism_{it}</i>	(8) <i>Deforestation_{it}</i>
<i>SoyCompetitionExposure_EU_{it-1}</i>	-1.23*** (0.28)							
<i>SoyExports_EU_{it}</i>		0.07 (0.08)	-0.14*** (0.03)	-124.89*** (33.80)				
<i>SoyCompetitionExposure_China_{it-1}</i>					- 8.67*** (0.95)			
<i>SoyExports_China_{it}</i>						-0.01 (0.01)	0.02*** (0.004)	19.29*** (4.04)
Cragg-Donald Wald F stat.		33.98				391.24		
Kleibergen-Paap Wald F-stat.		18.12				82.22		
Stock-Yogo weak ID test (10%)		16.38				16.38		
Observations	83,400	83,400	83,400	83,400	83,400	83,400	83,400	83,400
N. municipalities	5,560	5,560	5,560	5,560	5,560	5,560	5,560	5,560
Municipality FE and Year FE	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Initial conditions	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES

Notes: (a) robust standard errors in parentheses and clustered at municipality-level. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1. (b) Although our main analyses cover 2004-2018, we collected further data to construct the lagged variables, thus keeping the entire sample. (c) Both shift-share measures are standardized to $N(0, 1)$ for easier interpretation.

In columns 1-4 of Table 3 we report the impact of exposure to EU trade. Columns 5-8 show the findings related to the exposure to trade with China. All weak identification tests demonstrate that our instruments are sufficiently strong for predicting variations in the first stage. As expected, we find a negative relationship between the soy competition exposure and the volume of soy exports from Brazilian municipalities to the EU or China. Columns 2-4 indicate that a positive trade shock from the EU is associated with an increase in species richness, though this effect is not statistically significant. However, this shock is significantly associated with a decrease in both endemism and deforestation. In Columns 6-8, an increase in soy exports to China is linked to a non-significant decrease in species richness and to significant increase in both endemism and deforestation. While the findings related to species richness and deforestation are consistent with expectations, the unexpected finding on endemism is likely influenced by the pathways through which EU and Chinese trade affect biodiversity. One potential explanation is that EU trade impacts may predominantly occur in regions with a higher presence of endemic species. It is important to note that impact analysed here are average effects at a municipal scale.

Further details on the impact of trade on land use changes - direct conversion of forest to soy (*Forest_Soy*) and direct conversion of pastureland to soy (*Pasture_Soy*) is presented in Table 4. We observe a negative effect of increases in soy exports to the EU on the conversion of forests into soybean plantations (Column 1), while finding a positive effect on the conversion of pasturelands to soy cultivation (Column 2). Conversely, we find a positive impact of Chinese trade on forest-to-soybean conversion (Column 3), and a negative effect on the pasture-to-soy conversion (Column 4). These findings suggest that demand shocks from the EU are more closely linked to agricultural intensification, whereas extensification appears more characteristic of the trade shock from China.

Table 4. Effects of trade on land use changes

VARIABLES	(1) <i>Forest_Soy_{it}</i>	(2) <i>Pasture_Soy_{it}</i>	(3) <i>Forest_Soy_{it}</i>	(4) <i>Pasture_Soy_{it}</i>
$\widehat{SoyExports}_{EU_{it}}$	-0.34*** (0.09)	7.92*** (2.04)		
$\widehat{SoyExports}_{China_{it}}$			0.06*** (0.01)	-0.88*** (0.18)
Observations	83,400	83,400	83,400	83,400
Number of municipalities	5,560	5,560	5,560	5,560
Municipality FE and Year FE	YES	YES	YES	YES
Initial conditions	YES	YES	YES	YES

Notes: (a) robust standard errors in parentheses and clustered at municipality-level. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

CONCLUSION

The results from D3.3 demonstrate that commodity production is the main driver of biodiversity loss in the tropics in major exporting countries, such as Brazil and Indonesia. Importantly, our findings shed light on the complexity of the deforestation-biodiversity relationship. When analysing two types of value chain governance interventions, the results show that it is possible to achieve reductions in forest loss alongside improvements in certain dimensions of biodiversity, while other dimensions may remain unaffected or even experience negative impacts.

Our analysis of the Amazon Soy Moratorium reveals that the intervention successfully reduced deforestation and increased species richness and endemism but had no effect on phylogenetic diversity. Additionally, our findings suggest that midstream actors such as traders could serve as crucial change agents for new supply chain interventions and due diligence policies. Our analysis suggests that sticky soy traders were a mechanism through which changes in supply chain strategies influenced the impact of the Amazon Soy Moratorium. Using existing studies that employ market share-based treatment assignment as a benchmark, our estimates show that these actors account for about a quarter of the observed impact. These results offer valuable insights directly relevant to ongoing efforts of new deforestation-free regulations. However, understanding traders' willingness to expand conservation efforts to regions not covered by regulations remains a key pathway toward ending deforestation.

Further results illustrate the effects of soy trade on deforestation in Brazil, highlighting the role of exposure to international markets with different environmental preferences, specifically the EU and China. We find that (i) increased EU demand for soy results in reduced local deforestation, decreased endemism, and an increase in species richness, though the latter effect is not statistically significant.; (ii) increased demand for soy from China is associated with higher local deforestation, increased endemism, and a non-significant decline in species richness. These results reflect the non-linear nature of deforestation-biodiversity dynamics. Moreover, our analysis shows that EU demand shocks are associated with reduced forest-to-soybean conversion and increased pasture-to-soybean conversion, indicating a focus on agricultural intensification. Chinese trade shocks are linked to increased forest-to-soybean conversion and reduced pasture-to-soybean conversion, reflecting a trend toward extensification.

These findings carry significant policy implications. First, international trade can produce heterogeneous deforestation impacts in exporting regions, depending on the demand-side preferences for deforestation free products in the importing region. Both the EU and China are major importers of 'deforestation-risk' commodities and could thus potentially leverage market power in support of supply chain sustainability, but so far only the EU seems to have used its leverage to some extent. While this may sound like good news for advocates of mandatory due diligence policies like the EUDR, our results also caution against overreliance on an approach to fight deforestation by the value chain. Increasing demand from regions without dedicated due diligence policies continues to drive deforestation across soy producing regions according to our findings. Hence, the smaller the market share subject to due diligence, the larger the scope for leakage of deforestation to regions with a higher share of less scrutinized trade relationships. Moreover, some importing regions seem to be willing to accept soy from production regions with increasing deforestation risk, which leaves scope for sourcing patterns to adjust such that the EU imports soy from regions with low deforestation risk without actually reducing deforestation.

In sum, the ex-post econometric analyses of D3.3 empirically demonstrate that reductions in forest loss do not necessarily translate into biodiversity benefits. This underscores the importance of integrating innovative biodiversity modelling approaches, such as those developed in WP2, into standard practices for scholars evaluating the impact of trade on biodiversity. Adopting WP2's methodological framework can help address existing gaps in the literature by capturing the multiple

mechanisms through which trade and land-use changes affect biodiversity. While our analyses focus on direct measures of biodiversity, future research should also examine the trade-induced impacts on additional co-benefits, such as ecosystem services.

FUTURE WORK AND PUBLICATIONS

The empirical analyses presented herein are part of, or will become part of, scientific publications. The first ex-post econometric analysis (“*Amazon Soy Moratorium*”) is still ongoing, with revisions currently being undertaken by the researchers involved in WP3. More specifically, we plan to publish this work as scientific article(s), as outlined in Deliverable D8.4 (Dissemination, exploitation, and communication strategy III). One key concern that we are still addressing relates to the use of Cerrado municipalities and the potential issue of leakage. To test the robustness of our results, we are conducting and planning additional econometric exercises, including the use of matching procedures, the synthetic control method, and further analyses of heterogeneous treatment effects. Further analyses on the role of stickiness are also under consideration.

The second ex-post econometric analysis (“*Heterogeneous effects of soy export-market preferences*”) has already been revised and published in a well-regarded scientific journal, the *European Review of Agricultural Economics* (<https://doi.org/10.1093/erae/jbaf048>). Additional details on the underlying mechanisms, as well as on the estimation procedures, i.e., shift-share IV design rather than a gravity model, were incorporated at later stages of the publication process. The published article was accompanied by all data and code used in the analysis.

PROJECT OUTPUTS ACHIEVED

This deliverable “D3.3 Quantified ex-post impacts of trade in terrestrial biomass on biodiversity” contributes to Work Package 3 and CLEVER objective II ***“Provide empirical evidence for causal relationships between value chain governance initiatives and biodiversity impacts as well as related policy spillovers”***.

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Appendix A

Interview Guide – D3.3 “Quantified ex-post impacts of trade in terrestrial biomass on biodiversity”

Question 1) Could you briefly introduce yourself and provide an overview of your professional background?

Question 2) What is your perspective on the role of the Soy Moratorium in reducing deforestation impacts associated with agricultural production of this crop in the Amazon region? How do you perceive the discrepancies between the criteria of the moratorium and those outlined by the Forest Code? The Moratorium has undergone adjustments in the past (cut-off date); do you see potential for further adjustments in the governance of this initiative? If so, which adjustments would you suggest, and why?

Question 3) From the perspective of traders, how do they adapt their acquisition and trading strategies in response to varying market preferences concerning environmental impact? For example, a trader dealing with China may adopt different supply chain strategies compared to those trading with the European Union. What differences do you believe exist in terms of supply chains? How do these differences manifest in the relationships between traders and their suppliers (e.g., soybean producers)?

Question 4) Recent scientific literature has highlighted the importance of the concept of supply chain stickiness, which refers to the persistence of relationships with suppliers/buyers from the same location over time. What precisely defines 'stickiness' in the daily operations of traders with suppliers and buyers? How easy or difficult is it for a soybean trader to shift between supply regions and buying countries? What factors influence decisions to maintain or change these relationships?

Question 5) How do you believe this 'stickiness' could influence the implementation of new environmental policies (e.g., EUDR)? Did traders with different characteristics (such as supplier concentration or concentration of European buyers) respond differently during the implementation of the Soy Moratorium several years ago? If so, what were these different responses? Were characteristics related to the trade logic relevant?

Question 6) Are similar reactions observable in response to the European Union Regulation on deforestation-free products (EUDR)?

Question 7) In your view, how are the Soy Moratorium, the Forest Code, and the EUDR complementary or substitutive? Do you think new adjustments to all or some of these initiatives might arise?

Question 8) What do you consider to be the most important benefits and challenges for the implementation and enforcement of the EUDR in the Brazilian soy sector? What role do you foresee for the Plataforma Agro Brasil+Sustentável in this context?

Question 9) Is there anything else you would like to add that you consider important for us to consider? Is there anyone you believe we should speak with?

